

MYCOBACTERIUM TUBERCULOSIS METABOLISM

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Abstract

Highlighting the need for ongoing efforts in prevention, early identification, and easily available healthcare to successfully manage its spread. This article gives overview of mechanism of actions involed in anti-TB drugs, diagnosis and treatment for tuberculosis. The tuberculosis germs can transfer from person to person via air when the person with tuberculosis (TB) of lungs or throat coughs, or signs. Airborne TB can exist. People in the vicinity could inhale these germs and contract an infection. Tuberculosis is mainly a infectious disease that mainly affecting the lungs Around more than one million died due to tuberculosis. According to the WHO recent studies shows that about a quarter of the global population is estimated to have been infected with tuberculosis bacteria. Tuberculosis is also called a chronic granulomatous disease .

Keywords : Mycobacterium tuberculosis, granulomatous disease, lymph nodes, rifampicin and isoniazid.

Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) is an infectious bacterial disease which primarily affects the lungs parenchyma [4]. Tuberculosis is chronic granulomatous disease caused by bacteria called *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, which is an acid fast bacilli. It is resistant to intracellular killing, when it is ingested by phagocytes [9]. Tuberculosis is mainly a disease of lungs (pulmonary tuberculosis), but once the bacteria are inside the lungs, they cause immune system impairment and escape into blood and to infect other organs like the CNS, the lymphatic system, the genitourinary system, bones, joints, and even the skin. Other mycobacteria such as *Mycobacterium bovis*, *Mycobacterium africanum*, *Mycobacterium canetti*, and *Mycobacterium microticum* also cause tuberculosis [3].

Types of Tuberculosis

1. Primary tuberculosis

It is seen in person who have not been infected previously. The organism enters the body via lungs. Within an hour of reaching the lungs, the tubercle bacilli reach the draining lymph nodes at the hilum in the lungs and few organisms enter the systemic circulation.

Features

- Increased resistance is seen.
- T-cells (cellular immunity) prevent the spread of disease and the organisms remain inactive in the host.
- Reactivation of tubercle bacilli leads to progressive primary tuberculosis or military tuberculosis.

Morphology

Granulomatous lesions formed may consist of central necrotic material of cheesy nature (central caseation necrosis) or lack central necrotic material. It is surrounded by epithelioid cells and Langhans' giant cell with multiple nuclei.

2. Secondary tuberculosis

It is seen in persons who have been previously infected with primary lesions. It affects the apex in the lungs and other sites like tonsils, pharynx, larynx, small intestine and skin.

Features

- Caseous necrosis ruptures the blood vessels, thereby spreading the mitochondria throughout the body.
- Infection of the railway tract by mitochondria [30], [31].

Morphology

Lesions are located in the apex of one or both the lungs. The granuloma comprises epithelioid cells surrounded by fibroblasts, lymphocytes and Langerhans's giant cells. Some necrosis (caseation) is found in the centre of the tuberculosis [10].

Tuberculosis (TB) has become a major important global health problem. TB can be fatal if treatment is not taken. About 11 million people became ill with TB all over the world and about 1.5 million people worldwide died from TB in 2020 [16]. It is the second most deadly infectious disease (after COVID 19) and thirteenth leading cause of death in the world. But TB is treatable. The WHO estimates that TB treatment saved 74 million lives between 2000 and 2021 [17].

Periodically bacteria that develop TB resistance can result in drug-resistant tuberculosis. Thus, the medication is no longer able to eradicate the TB bacteria [2].

The main obstacle to TB control and elimination is drug-resistant TB (DR-TB). The same methods used to propagate drug-susceptible TB also work to spread drug-resistant TB (DR-TB) [18]. Drug-resistant tuberculosis develops when tuberculosis medications are abused or improperly handled. The germs that cause multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) can develop resistant against isoniazid and rifampicin, the two major effective TB medications. All patients with tuberculosis are treated with these medications. Treatment for MDR-TB should involve consultation with TB specialists [10][20]. According to the Global TB report 2021, 132,222 cases of RR-TB and MDR-TB were found in 2020. The rise of MDR- and RR-TB is a serious risk to the control of tuberculosis and is a growing worry for public health worldwide [18]. Pre-Extensively Drug-resistant TB is the subtype of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) that is caused by either tuberculosis bacteria resistant to fluoroquinolone, rifampicin, and/or isoniazid, as well as a second-line injectable (capreomycin, kanamycin and amikacin) [14]. A uncommon kind of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB), extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis (XDR-TB) is caused by tuberculosis bacteria which are resistant to capreomycin, kanamycin, and amikacin, the second-line injectable, as well as to isoniazid and rifampicin [9]. Alternatively, by TB bacteria resistant to bedaquiline, linezolid, fluoroquinolone,

rifampicin, and isoniazid. Patients are allocated with far less effective therapy options since extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis is impervious to the strongest TB medications [18], [20].

Aetiology

Tuberculosis is communicable chronic granulomatous disease caused by bacteria called *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* [2]. It usually involves the lungs but may affect any organ or tissue in the body. Typically the centres of tubercular granulomas undergo caseous necrosis [7]. TB is basically caused by tubercle bacilli, which belong to the genus *Mycobacterium*. *Mycobacterium* species include: *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, *Mycobacterium bovis*, *Mycobacterium africanum*, *Mycobacterium leprae*, the cause of leprosy. The tuberculosis germs can transfer from person to person via air when the person with tuberculosis (TB) of lungs or throat coughs, or sings. Airborne TB can exist. People in the vicinity could inhale these germs and contract an infection [16].

Pathophysiology

Tuberculosis is an infectious disease which occurs when a droplet nuclei containing tubercle bacilli is inhaled. Inhaled droplet nuclei quickly reaches the terminal bronchioles and alveoli in the lungs and thereby prevents the activation of defense mechanisms in the upper airways. Soon after the entry of bacilli into the lung, alveolar macrophages ingest them but fail to destroy them. Consequently, the bacilli start multiplying within the macrophages. As the bacilli proliferate, the macrophages improve their ability to destroy the bacilli. Development of T-lymphocytes and macrophages capable of destroying and controlling the infection constitute the cell-mediated response. When the pathogens inhaled are low and host has an intact immune system, the containment (destruction) and control of bacilli results in the formation of a grey-white granulomatous lesion in lung called Ghon's focus (primary lung lesion). When large number of pathogens are inhaled and the host has a compromised immune system, the hypersensitivity reactions produced by the bacilli causes the Ghon's focus to undergo caseous (pasty, yellow and cheese-like) necrosis. The bacilli which are present within the Ghon's focus to drain along the lymph channels and reach lymph nodes of the affected lung and form further caseous granulomas. Ghon's focus and the granulomas that form in the lymph nodes are together called as Ghon's complex. Due to inflammatory and immune response, Ghon's complex undergoes

healing. However if body's defense mechanism fail, then primary infection develops into secondary tuberculosis [5].

Signs and symptoms

A patient with active tuberculosis presents the following clinical manifestations.

1. Fatigue, fever, night sweats and loss of weight, loss of appetite.
2. Cough which is initially nonproductive but is accompanied by purulent sputum in the later stages. The production of sputum is triggered by inflammation and tissue necrosis.
3. Patient, though rarely, may cough up blood in the sputum(haemoptysis).
4. Chest pain and hoarseness of the voice.
5. Loss of muscle, phlegm, severe unintentional weight loss, shortness of breath, or swollen lymph nodes [11], [13].

Risk factors

- Low body weight
- HIV infection
- Diabetes mellitus
- Organ transplants
- Silicosis
- Alcoholism
- Medical treatment such like corticosteroids [14]
- Tobacco smoking
- Poverty, overcrowding and poor housing (socio-economic factors)
- Malnutrition (biological factors) [12]
- Long-term use of prescription steroids
- Severe kidney disease
- Organ transplantation [15].

Tuberculosis drugs and Metabolism of action

First-Line Treatment of TB for Drug-Sensitive TB

Fig 1: Shows here are the four drugs in the standard regimen of first-line drugs. Also the dates of the four drugs were discovered besides 40 years ago are shown.

Cycloserine, ethambutol, thioamides, and nitroimidazoles all affect the synthesis of cell walls. ATP synthase is inhibited by diarylquinoline. Aminoglycosides, Cyclic Peptides, PAS, and Fluoroquinolones all affect DNA. First-line medications taken day-to-day for several months can cure tuberculosis, which give rise to bacterial infection *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*[2].

Isoniazid is one of the superlative antitubercular drug. It is used as a first line treatment for tuberculosis and also in chemoprophylaxis. INH is easily absorbed from the gut, distributed all over the body, including tubercular cavities and body fluids like CSF, and crosses the placental barrier. It is metabolized by acetylation, and the metabolites are excreted in urine. ADR: Hepatotoxicity, Peripheral neuritis, skin rashes, arthralgia, GI disturbances, psychosis, fever, anaemia and infrequently convulsions [1].

Rifampicin is a first-line antitubercular medication that is derived from rifamycin. Both internal and external bacilli, including spurters, are quickly destroyed by it. Since rifampicin is the sole agent that can affect all bacillary subpopulations, it is referred to as a sterilizing agent. Rifampicin suppresses RNA production by binding to the DNA-dependent RNA polymerase in bacteria [20]. It is bactericidal to mycobacteria, E. Coli, pseudomonas, H. influenza, and other microorganisms. When taken orally, it enters the body quickly and is absorbed in GI tract; however, the presence of food inhibits its absorption. It is then dispersed all over the body and processed in the liver. The deacetylated version that is active is eliminated through bile and passes through enterohepatic recycling [23]. ADR – GI disturbances like nausea, vomiting, and abdominal discomfort. Itching, skin rashes and flushing. Hepatitis, hepatotoxicity, fever, chills, headache, muscle and joint pain .

Pyrazinamide Nicotinamide has a synthetic equivalent called pyrazinamide. It works effectively against intracellular bacilli in an acidic pH. It exhibits tuberculocidal properties. Pyrazinamide works through a different mechanism than INH to prevent the formation of mycobacterial mycolic acid. When taken orally, it is absorbed from the GI tract and dispersed all over the body, including the CSF. Urine is formed by liver's metabolism. ADRs include skin rashes, fever, nausea, vomiting, anorexia, hyperuricaemia, and dose-dependent hepatotoxicity[31] .

Ethambutol The first-line antitubercular medication is ethambutol. It prevents the formation of the arabinosyltransferases which is necessary for the mycobacterial cell wall. This medication is bacteriostatic. It is combined with other anti-TB medications to expedite the conversion of sputum and prevent the establishment of resistance. Following oral treatment, ethambutol is extensively absorbed, transported throughout the body, processed in the liver, crosses the blood-brain barrier in cases of meningitis, and eliminated in the urine. ADRs include hyperuricaemia, itching, joint discomfort, rashes on the skin, nausea, vomiting, and optical neuritis[31].

Multidrug-resistant Tuberculosis (MDR-TB) and Second-Line Treatments

Fig 2: When a strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* develops resistance to two of the major potent first-line medications, isoniazid and rifampicin, MDR TB results.

Healthcare professionals must use combinations of second-line medications, some of which are listed here, to treat MDR-TB. In comparison to first-line therapy, second-line drugs may result in more side effects, require longer treatment periods, and cost up to 100 times as much. Treatment can become even more difficult when MDR TB strains develop resistance to second-line medications [9], [28].

Para-aminosalicylic Acid (PAS)

The medication PAS is a second-line drug which is used in treatment for tuberculosis. It inhibits the enzyme folate synthetase competitively and stops tetrahydrofolic acid (THFA) from forming, which is essential for bacterial growth and multiplication. Consequently, PAS has a tuberculostatic effect. Following oral ingestion, PAS is quickly absorbed, dispersed throughout the body, metabolised by acetylation in the liver, and eliminated in the urine. It is a standby medication for treating MDR-TB ADRs, or gastrointestinal disorders, which include anorexia, and pain in the abdomen, liver impairment, thrombocytopenia, skin rashes, and drug fever [31].

Ethionamide

Although it is less effective than INH, ethionamide shares a similar structure. It prevents mycolic acid from being synthesised. It works against both external and intracellular bacilli and is classified as a bacteriostatic medication. Following oral administration, it is well absorbed and dispersed throughout the entire body, including the CSF. Urine is formed by liver's metabolism.

ADRs include headache, blurred vision, hepatitis, nausea, vomiting, and paraesthesia [3].

Extensively Drug-Resistant Tuberculosis (XDR-TB) – Options for Treatment

Fig 3: Two new medications are Delamanid and Bedaquiline. Potentially useful medications include ethambutol, pyrazinamide, thioamides, cycloserine, PAS, streptomycin, and clofazimine. Injectable second-line medications are capreomycin, kanamycin and amikacin.

Mechanism of Action of available TB medications

Fig 4: Cycloserine, ethambutol, thioamides, and nitroimidazoles all affect the synthesis of cell walls. ATP synthase is inhibited by diarylquinoline. Aminoglycosides, Cyclic Peptides, PAS, and Fluoroquinolones all affect DNA.

Drugs for tuberculosis aim to inhibit the synthesis of proteins, nucleic acids, and cell walls, among other aspects of the analysis of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. The exact mechanisms of action of some medications are still unknown [8], [24].

New Candidate TB Drugs that are being developed

Fig 5: The list below includes a number of novel TB medications that are presently in development. Five of these compounds—denoted by asterisks (*) above—were developed with support from NIAID: SQ-109, PA-824 (Pretomanid), Meropenem, Linezolid and Sutezolid.

Mechanism of Actions of TB Drugs Being Developed

Fig 6: SQ-109, benzothiazinones, meropenem, and nitroimidazoles all affect the synthesis of cell walls. ATP production is inhibited by imidazopyridine amide. Macrolides, rifamycins, and oxybenzolidinones all affect DNA.

Drugs for tuberculosis aim to inhibit the synthesis of proteins, nucleic acids, and cell walls, among other aspects of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*'s biology. The exact mechanisms of action of some medications are still unknown[21].

Diagnosis

To diagnosis a tuberculosis (TB) infection, some TB tests are conducted. They are

Skin Test: An applicator covered with dried tuberculin reagent or a comparable device coated with liquid tuberculin just prior to application are both used in the multiple puncture approach. An injector is used in the Heaf method. Inside the single forearm, a little amount of a drug known as tuberculin is injected just beneath the skin. A medical professional will examine your arm at the injection site for swelling within 48 to 72 hours. A positive or negative test result is determined by the size of the raised skin. This test looks for evidence that your immune system has developed an antibody against TB. Patient might have active TB disease or a latent infection, if test results are positive. Individuals who had a tuberculosis vaccination may test positive even in the absence of infection. If the test is negative, it indicates that your body did not respond to it. It does not imply that you are immune to infections [26].

Blood tests: A lab receives a sample of blood. The ability of specific immune system cells to "recognize" tuberculosis is tested in a lab. A positive test indicates the presence of either a current TB disease or a latent TB infection. Determining whether you have an active disease can be aided by additional blood testing. If the test is negative, most likely patient does not have tuberculosis [28].

X-ray: An X-ray of the chest will reveal atypical patches in the lungs, indicative of active tuberculosis [27].

Sputum test: Sputum that comes up when you cough, is something your doctor may want to sample. Lab testing are able to identify the bacteria if you have active tuberculosis in your voice box or lungs. If the sputum is likely to include the TB bacterium, this can be determined by a simple lab test. However, it might be displaying microorganisms with comparable traits. The existence of TB germs can be verified by another laboratory test. Results usually take a few weeks to appear. If the bacteria is drug-resistant, a lab test can also determine this. This data aids your healthcare professional in selecting the most appropriate course of action [22].

Further lab tests that are conducted are:

- Breath test.
- Urine test.
- Test of the fluid all over the spine and brain, called cerebrospinal fluid [28].

Treatment

Not everyone infected with TB bacteria becomes sick. As a result, two TB-related conditions exist: latent TB infection and TB disease. Both latent TB infection and TB disease can be treated [19]. Without treatment latent TB infection can leads to advancement of TB disease. If not treated properly, TB disease can become fatal [21]. There are so many treatment regimens are recommended in US for latent TB infection. The drugs used to treat latent-TB infection are:

- Isoniazid (INH)
- Rifampicin (RIF)
- Rifapentine (RPT)

The following table illustrates how these drugs can be used singly or in combination. One-weekly isoniazid plus rifapentine for three months is one example of a short-term regimen (3HP)

Rifampicin (4R) used daily for four months

Daily isoniazid + rifampicin for three months (3HR)

Isoniazid monotherapy, which lasts six to nine months (6H/9H), is less effective, safer, and less likely to be finished than short-term treatment programmes such as 4R and 3HP. Compared to

6H and 9H, shorter rifamycin-based treatment regimens frequently carry a lower risk of hepatotoxicity [6]. If short-course treatment regimens are not feasible or accessible, 6H and 9H are effective alternative regimens for latent tuberculosis infections. Though effective, 6H and 9H have lower treatment completion rates and a higher risk of toxicity when compared to most short-term treatment regimens [25] .

If the patient comes into contact with a person who has drug-resistant tuberculosis, then all forms of treatment need to be adjusted [17]. Based on concurrent medical problems (such as HIV), probable drug-drug interactions, and the drug susceptibility results of the suspected source case (if known), clinicians should determine the best course of treatment. If drug-resistant TB is present in the source of TB infection known, consulting a TB specialist is recommended [21] [27].

Conclusion

This review article consists of following key points are Mycobacterium tuberculosis is the chronic infectious illness that causes tuberculosis. It is still a worldwide health concern despite therapeutic advances, highlighting the need for ongoing efforts in prevention, early identification, and easily available healthcare to successfully manage its spread. In conclusion If the right policies are implemented, clinical and public health management is ensured to be effective, and efforts from both inside and outside the health sector are dedicated and coordinated, tuberculosis can be contained. This article gives overview of mechanism of actions involved in anti-TB drugs, diagnosis and treatment for tuberculosis.

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